

Title: Using Computer vision with data generators to train more samples variations

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INTRODUCTION:

Many complex problems from Autonomous and Healthcare fields not have enough dataset for deep learning training. This problem forced us to deal with a very small dataset (~1000 sample) and get the accuracy near 100% because in this field safety is the highest priority.

AIM:

Generate a huge number of variations (10000% - 20000%) of the original dataset. to reach 95% - 99% accuracy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Two datasets from autonomous and healthcare fields, one for traffic light classification and one for skin disease classifications. Train Convolutional neural network using Keras running on top of TensorFlow. And create random variation using Computer vision functions such as (flip, rotation, illumination, contrast, transform)

RESULTS:

More than 99% accuracy for traffic light classification and ~95% accuracy for healthcare application.

CONCLUSIONS:

The accuracy increased by 10%-20% with generating more variation from original dataset using computer vision and keras data generators

KEYWORDS:

Deep Learning, Computer Vision, autonomous vehicles, healthcare

BIOGRAPHY:

Mahmood is currently Self Driving Car Mentor at Udacity, Deep Learning Engineer. Prior to that, He worked as data acquisition supervisor at Nielsen. AI, Autonomous, Deep Learning, Computer Vision and Data analysis enthusiast.